

[SPIRE/STRATOS GNSS-PRO] Quality Assessment Summary

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
1.0	04/02/2025	First draft with GNSS-RO data analysis
1.1	10/12/2025	GNSS-PRO data analysis included in the document
1.2	12/12/2025	Minor editing changes
1.3	20/03/2026	Minor editing addressing comments from SPIRE
1.4	20/04/2026	Minor editing addressing comments from SPIRE and updating the Maturity matrix grades

REFERENCE

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v2.2, 6th December 2022.
- RD-2. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework - Atmospheric Guidelines, EDAP.REP.061, v0.1, October 2021
- RD-3. SPIRE Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description v1.0
- RD-4. SPIRE Level 1 PRO Product Description v1.0 and v1.1
- RD-5. SPIRE Level 0 Raw RO Product Description v1.0
- RD-6. SPIRE Level 0 Raw PRO Product Description v1.0
- RD-7. SPIRE Attitude and Navigation Product Summary v1.1
- RD-8. Summary Spire Level 1D Polarimetric RO Product Description v1.0
- RD-9. EDAP Technical Note on SPIRE/STRATOS (GNSS-RO) Quality Assessment Summary, EDAP.REP.017, v1.2. URL: <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/documents/20142/37627/Technical+Note+on+Quality+Assessment+for+SPIRE.pdf/cf350d81-da28-9dc2-7d01-7953d34fe2bc>
- RD-10. Cardellach, E., Oliveras, S., Rius, A., Tomás, S., Ao, C. O., Franklin, G. W., et al. (2019). Sensing heavy precipitation with GNSS polarimetric radio occultations. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 46, 1024-1031. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL080412>
- RD-11. Gorbunov, M. E., Shmakov, A. V., Leroy, S. S., Lauritsen, K. B., COSMIC Radio Occultation Processing: Cross-Center Comparison and Validation. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 28, 737- 751, 2011.
- RD-12. Gorbunov, M.E., Shmakov, A.V. Statistically average atmospheric bending angle model based on COSMIC experimental data. *Izv. Atmos. Ocean. Phys.* **52**, 622–628 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0001433816060050>

- RD-13. Gorbunov, M. E. and Lauritsen, K. B., Analysis of wave fields by Fourier Integral Operators and its application for radio occultations, *Radio Science*, 39(4), RS4010, doi:10. 1029/2003RS002971, 2004.
- RD-14. Rocken, C. et al., Analysis and validation of GPS/MET data in the neutral atmosphere. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 102, 29849-29866, 1997.
- RD-15. Durre, I., Yin, X., Vose, R. S., Applequist, S., & Arnfield, J., 2018: Enhancing the Data Coverage in the Integrated Global Radiosonde Archive, *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 35(9), 1753-1770. DOI:10.1175/JTECH-D-17-0223.1. [Overview of enhancements and data additions that resulted in IGRA version 2.0.]
- RD-16. Picone, J. M., et al. NRLMSISE-00 empirical model of the atmosphere: Statistical comparisons and scientific issues. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 2002, 107.A12: SIA 15-1-SIA 15-16.
- RD-17. Tschanz, B., Straub, C., Scheiben, D., Walker, K. A., Stiller, G. P., and Kämpfer, N.: Validation of middle-atmospheric campaign-based water vapour measured by the ground-based microwave radiometer MIAWARA-C, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 6, 1725–1745, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-6-1725-2013>, 2013.
- RD-18. Mevi, G., Muscari, G., Bertagnolio, P. P., Fiorucci, I., and Pace, G.: VESPA-22: a ground-based microwave spectrometer for long-term measurements of polar stratospheric water vapor, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 11, 1099–1117, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-11-1099-2018>, 2018.
- RD-19. Waugh, D. W., Sobel, A. H., & Polvani, L. M. (2017). What Is the Polar Vortex and How Does It Influence Weather?. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 98(1), 37-44. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-15-00212.1>
- RD-20. Huffman, G.J., E.F. Stocker, D.T. Bolvin, E.J. Nelkin, Jackson Tan (2023), GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 Half Hourly 0.1 degree x 0.1 degree V07, Greenbelt, MD, Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC), Accessed: [01/04/2024], [10.5067/GPM/IMERG/3B-HH/07](https://doi.org/10.5067/GPM/IMERG/3B-HH/07)
- RD-21. Product User Manual (PUM) for product H60B, H63/P-IN-SEVIRI-PMW, P-IN-SEVIRI_E Precipitation rate at ground by GEO/IR supported by LEO/MW, <https://hsaf.meteoam.it/Products/Detail?prod=H60B>
- RD-22. E. Cardellach *et al.*, "Sensitivity of PAZ LEO Polarimetric GNSS Radio-Occultation Experiment to Precipitation Events," in *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 190-206, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2014.2320309
- RD-23. Cardellach, E., Oliveras, S., Rius, A., Tomás, S., Ao, C. O., Franklin, G. W., et al. (2019). Sensing heavy precipitation with GNSS polarimetric radio occultations. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 46, 1024–1031. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL080412>
- RD-24. Padullés, R., Cardellach, E., Turk, F.J., Ao, C.O., de la Torre Juárez, M., Gong, J. and Wu, D.L., 2021. Sensing horizontally oriented frozen particles with polarimetric radio occultations aboard PAZ: Validation using GMI coincident observations and Cloudsat a priori information. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 60, pp.1-13.

- RD-25. Padullés, R., Cardellach, E., Paz, A., Oliveras, S., Hunt, D. C., Sokolovskiy, S., ... & de la Torre Juárez, M. (2024). The PAZ polarimetric radio occultation research dataset for scientific applications. *Earth System Science Data Discussions*, 2024, 1-28.
- RD-26. Hotta, D., Lonitz, K., & Healy, S. (2023). Forward operator for polarimetric radio occultation measurements. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques Discussions*, 2023, 1-20.
- RD-27. Wang, K. N., Ao, C. O., Padullés, R., Turk, F. J., Juárez, M. D. L. T., & Cardellach, E. (2022). The effects of heavy precipitation on polarimetric radio occultation (PRO) bending angle observations. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 39(2), 149-161.
- RD-28. Talpe, M. J., Nguyen, V. A., & Tomás, S. (2025). Initial Polarimetric Radio Occultation Results from Spire's Nanosatellite Constellation: Satellite Payload, Collection, and Calibration. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 106(4), E714-E734.
- RD-29. Padullés, Ramon, et al. "Initial polarimetric radio occultation results from Spire's nanosatellite constellation: Independent assessment and potential applications." *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 106.4 (2025): E735-E751.
- RD-30. ESA PROGRES project: Development of a 3U nanosatellite equipped with an innovative Polarimetric Radio Occultation (PRO) demonstration sensor to detect and characterize precipitation, with the goal of creating a commercial data product for assimilation or direct use. <https://incubed.esa.int/portfolio/progres/>
- RD-31. Jing, Xin, et al. "Spire RO thermal profiles for climate studies: initial comparisons of the measurements from spire, NOAA-20 ATMS, Radiosonde, and COSMIC-2." *Remote Sensing* 15.15 (2023): 3710.

GLOSSARY

- AEE:** Agencia Espacial Española
- ATBD:** Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
- BA:** Bending angle
- EDAP:** Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot
- EO:** Earth Observation
- EM:** Electromagnetic
- ESA:** European Space Agency

- GEO:** Geostationary Earth Orbit
- GNSS:** Global Navigation Satellite System
- IGRA:** Integrated Global Radiosonde Archive
- LEO:** Low Earth Orbit
- MM:** Maturity Matrix
- RO:** Radio Occultation
- PRO:** Polarimetric Radio Occultation
- PAZ:** (Spanish for "peace") satellite

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this work we perform the assessment of SPIRE GNSS-PRO data provided in the frame of EDAP+. Spire's constellation in low Earth orbit (LEO) continuously gathers data from occulted GNSS signals to generate profiles of atmospheric variables through the radio occultation (RO) technique,

Figure 1.1. Each RO satellite is equipped with a custom receiver that tracks GNSS signals at two frequencies using multiple antennas. In 2023, Spire launched three polarimetric RO (PRO) satellites, enhancing traditional RO observations. These satellites are equipped with a polarimetric RO antenna, which simultaneously tracks the horizontal (H) and vertical (V) polarization components of the incoming occulted signal. As evidenced by the PAZ mission results [RD-10], the phase difference between the linear polarization components correlates with hydrometeors presence (water droplets, ice crystals, snow, grapel, etc.) and other parameters along the signal path. Each occulted signal is typically tracked at a 50 Hz sampling rate using a state-of-the-art, open-loop tracking technique that utilizes an a priori atmospheric model to aid GNSS signal tracking.

This assessment has been performed on GNSS-PRO data and atmospheric RO products to study atmospheric profiles, collected by the SPIRE's sensors. Separate analyses are performed and reported in this document. The grade results in the Maturity Matrix were evaluated following the EDAP best practices and atmospheric guidelines [RD-1, RD-2].

The GNSS-PRO dataset analysed is composed of multiple Level 1 products, named *L1C polPhs*, *L1D resPrf* and *L1D hdrPhs*, because of the novel nature of the data pipeline chain

We received over 300,000 profiles of L1C polPhs and, as a courtesy from Spire, 5 example profiles of L1D resPrf and hdrPhs derived from the L1C polPhs. L1D resPrf is based on the newly established standard described [RD-25]. L1C polPhs and L1D hdrPhs are internal Spire products. In the scientific community, there is no established algorithm to retrieve precipitation from the L1 PRO observable of differential phase shift. But large-scale correlation between this differential phase shift observable and precipitation has still been established in PAZ datasets [RD-24] and Spire datasets [RD-28, RD-29], following the ESA PROGRES project [RD-30].

In this work we focused on analysing and reporting the differences between the different SPIRE levels content, with the focus on the precipitation information. Reference data used for the precipitation is GPM IMERG final precipitation L3 [RD-20].

The RO *L2_patmPrf* products comprises tropospheric vertical profiles of temperature and pressure, global coverage and almost 6 months temporal coverage (from 2023-05-15 to 2023-11-30), collected by the three GNSS-PRO satellites, FM 166, 167 and 170. The intercomparison exercise has been carried out using the Integrated Global Radiosonde Archive (IGRA) dataset [RD-15] as reference dataset.

A first assessment of SPIRE GNSS-RO atmospheric products has been performed during the previous EDAP contract in 2019 [RD-9]. This new validation is meant for checking the data quality of L2 products generated by the improved STRATOS GNSS-PRO sensor. Recently, NOAA and EUMETSAT have officially accepted RO-from-PRO for their operational purposes [RD-28].

A total of 1260 SPIRE-IGRA coupled measurements were obtained by matching the data using temporal and geographic thresholds of 1h and 100 km. The co-located couples were filtered out based on SPIRE quality flag, resulting in 861 final co-located measurements emplaced for the analysis. To take atmospheric variability into account, the analyses were performed by altitude and latitude. With regression values close to ideal and a correlation coefficient of 0.95, SPIRE and IGRA data match well between 10 and 30 km altitude region. Since water vapour is not accounted for in a-priori models, SPIRE measurements diverge below the tropopause, as can be seen in the reduced divergence at the South Pole, because the region's low water vapour reduces the impact.

Figure 1.1 scheme of GNSS-RO technique concept. The GPS/GNSS satellite at GEO orbit send electromagnetic (EM) pulses that reaches the Earth. The SPIRE GNSS receivers are mounted on satellites at LEO orbits that receive those signals in occultation configuration. The received signal is distorted by the atmosphere, applying inversion algorithm it is possible to obtain information about the atmospheric parameters.

2. CALVAL MATURITY MATRICES

Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

This assessment aims to review mission quality as evidenced by its documentation. It is divided into the follow sections:

- Product Information
- Metrology
- Product Generation
- Validation Summary

SPIRE GNSS-PRO Evaluation

Table 2.1 SPIRE GNSS-PRO Maturity Matrix

SPIRE GNSS-PRO Data Provider Documentation Review			SPIRE GNSS-PRO Validation Summary	Key	
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		Not Assessed	Not Assessable
Product Details	Basic	Good			
Availability & Accessibility	Excellent	Ideal			
Product Format, Flags & Metadata Not Public					
User Documentation					
	Ancillary Data				

SPIRE GNSS-PRO Validation Maturity Matrix

Table 2.2 SPIRE GNSS-PRO detailed validation

SPIRE GNSS-PRO Detailed Validation			
Measurement		Geometric	
SPIRE GNSS-PRO vs GPM IMERGE Validation Activity Method	SPIRE GNSS-PRO vs GPM IMERGE Validation Results Compliance	SPIRE GNSS-PRO vs GPM IMERGE Geometric Validation Method	SPIRE GNSS-PRO vs GPM IMERGE Geometric Validation Results Compliance

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Good
Excellent
Ideal
Not Public

SPIRE GNSS-PRO Data Provider Documentation Review

Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Ideal	
Justification	<i>All required information available.</i> We recommend the provider to update the version number inside each product with the associated documentation.
Product Name	SPIRE GNSS-PRO
Sensor Name	STRATOS
Sensor Type	GNSS Receiver
Mission Type	Constellation – 3 satellites FM166 (LEMUR-2-PHILARI) FM167 (LEMUR-2-MMOLO) FM170 (LEMUR-2-ROMEO-N-LEO)
Mission Orbit	FM 166 and FM 167 550-km-altitude, sun-synchronous orbit with a 0930 local time of the descending node. FM 170 520-km altitude, sun-synchronous orbit with a 1030 local time of the ascending node
Product Version Number	L1C_polPhs: from product attribute v1.0, from filename v06.02, from doc not reported L1D_hdrPhs: from product attribute v06.03, from doc [RD-8] v06.03 L1D_resPrf: from product attribute v00_6, from doc [RD-8] v06.04
Product ID	L1C_polPhs, L1D_hdrPhs, L1D_resPrf
Processing level of product	Level 1C, Level 1D
Measured Quantity Name	<p>L1C_polPhs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Satellite navigation coordinates [km, km/s] Atmospheric excess phase delay on L1 and L2 channels [m] Excess Phase on L1 and L2 Channels for both vertical and horizontal polarizations [m] <p>L1D_hdrPhs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differential excess delay with no offset correction [Rad] Height above mean sea level as function of acquisition time [km] <p>L1D_resPrf:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smoothed differential phase shift into 0.1 km vertical grid [mm] Smoothed differential phase shift standard deviation [mm] Height above mean sea level [km] “rays” variable that allows to visualize the Area of Interest (AOI) scanned during the acquisition, latitude, longitude and altitude on which each grid point contributes to the collected differential phase shift profile [km].L2 atmospheric variable (Refractivity [1], Dry Temperature [K], Dry Pressure [hPa])
Measured Quantity Units	<p>L1C_polPhs: [km, km/s, m]</p> <p>L1D_hdrPhs: [Rad, km]</p> <p>L1D_resPrf: [mm, km, 1, K, hPa]</p>
Stated Measurement Quality	The differential phase observable has a precision of about 0.5 mm.

Spatial Resolution	<p>Vertical: The nominal observed straight line tangent altitude range of each occultation event spans from less than -150 km to approximately 170 km for L1 data.</p> <p>Horizontal: L1D_refPrf products have “rays” variables that allows to visualize the Area of Interest (AOI) scanned during the acquisition, latitude, longitude and the altitude each point contributes to the differential phase shift profile.</p> <p>For each point provided in the vector of points within a profile, the spatial resolution is on the order of ~100 m vertically and ~10 km horizontally.</p> <p>References: [RD-4], [RD-28]</p>
Spatial Coverage	Global
Temporal Resolution	<p>An exact revisit time cannot be computed because the measurements are opportunistic in nature. A Spire PRO satellite orbiting in LEO and collecting GNSS transmissions will typically have measurements across a 100-1000 km wide swath depending on the tangent point altitude. As most Spire satellites are in high-inclination orbits, the Earth is regularly covered.</p> <p>Reference: [RD-4]</p>
Temporal Coverage	2023 – still ongoing
Point of Contact	Spire: Global Data and Analytics
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<p>Products available through ESA TPM portal:</p> <p>https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/announcement-of-opportunity/announcement-of-opportunity-for-spire-data</p> <p>https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/catalog/spire-live-and-historical-data</p>
Conditions for access and use	Commercial data; part of dataset is freely available through ESA Earth online: Spire live and historical data - Earth Online (esa.int)
Limitations on public access	L1C_polPhs available through ESA TPM portal The other products are not public
Product Abstract	GNSS-PRO measurements of excess phase delay collected by three SPIRE GNSS-PRO satellites.

Availability & Accessibility																																							
Grade: Good																																							
Justification	Data partially follow FAIR principles. The grade can be upgrade to Excellent if the data management plan is provided																																						
Compliant with FAIR principles	Partially compliant																																						
	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td colspan="2">To be Findable:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes, the file name is generated univocally</td> </tr> <tr> <td>data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes</td> <td style="text-align: center;">No, the version number is not always updated</td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource</td> <td style="text-align: center;">No</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">To be Accessible:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes, on ESA portal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes, on ESA portal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes, on ESA portal</td> </tr> <tr> <td>metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available</td> <td style="text-align: center;">No</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">To be Interoperable:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes, the file L1B that generates the data</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">To be Reusable:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Yes</td> </tr> </table>	To be Findable:		(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Yes, the file name is generated univocally	data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	Yes	metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes	No, the version number is not always updated	(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	No	To be Accessible:		(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	Yes, on ESA portal	the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	Yes, on ESA portal	the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	Yes, on ESA portal	metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	No	To be Interoperable:		(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	Yes	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	Yes	(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	Yes, the file L1B that generates the data	To be Reusable:		meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	Yes.	(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	Yes	R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	Yes	R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	Yes
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R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	Yes																																						
Data Management Plan	No																																						
Availability Status	Part of data are available on request to ESA Earth online portal. This dataset is distributed through FAIR principles.																																						

Product Format, Flags & Metadata	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Data are distributed in a documented standard file format. Product structure follows the PAZ product structure [RD-4]. Includes a good set of documented metadata and data flags. Some variables should be more detailed described in the metadata or in the user guide. We suggest reporting description of some important metadata such as <i>"height_flag"</i> directly in the documentation and in the product attributes, even if it is described in the referenced scientific paper
Product File Format	<i>netCDF4, BUFR</i>
Metadata Conventions	Metadata follow the PAZ product structure. L1 data file format is similar to the one used by the COSMIC Data Analysis and Archive Center (CDAAC) for the COSMIC-1 radio occultation mission.
Analysis Ready Data?	No

User Documentation		
Grade: Good		
Justification	Some PUG and ATBD-type information available, recovered from multiple documentation and internal communications. Documentation is up to date. Documentation is also partially compliant with QA4ECV.	
<i>Document</i>	<i>References</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spire PRO Level 1 Product Description • Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description • Talpe et al. 2025 [RD-28] 	<i>Partially</i>
ATBD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spire PRO Level 1 Product Description • Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description • Talpe et al. 2025 [RD-28] 	<i>Partially</i>

Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>Pre-flight and post-launch measurement calibration & characterisation efforts cover all reasonable aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is “fit for purpose” in terms of the mission’s stated performance.</p> <p>From documentation:</p> <p>The differential phase shift is affected by the antenna response. As noted in Talpe et al. (2025) and confirmed in Padullés et al. (2025), the response of antennas onboard Spire satellites was characterized on the ground, matched with on-orbit measurements, and shown to have little to no impact on the final differential phase shift observable. Therefore, the measurement can be considered properly calibrated. Future satellites will also undergo on-orbit antenna response characterization. Please see Section 3.c.1 in Talpe et al. (2025) for further details on antenna response and calibration.</p>
References	<p>Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4] Talpe et al. 2025 [RD-28] Padullés et al. (2025) [RD-29]</p>

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>Geometric calibration & characterisation covers all reasonable aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is “fit for purpose” in terms of the mission’s stated performance.</p> <p>The geometric characterization is done using GPS constellation data. The AOI is estimated in L1D_resPrf products, and satellite navigation data are provided in L1C_polPhs products.</p> <p>Navigation data are given with the respect to the Earth Centered Inertial Frame and not as latitude, longitude coordinates.</p> <p>In our judgement the method for calculating the geometrical location should be accurate using the GPS that is the best geolocation method so far.</p> <p>Each product has a footprint of tens of km projected on the surface; the geolocation method should be considered fit for purpose for such kind of application.</p>
References	<p>Spire PRO Level 1 Product Description [RD-4] Summary Spire Level 1D Polarimetric RO Product Description [RD-8]</p>

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Traceability chain documented identifying most important steps and sources of uncertainty.
References	Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4] Summary Spire Level 1D Polarimetric RO Product Description [RD-8]
Traceability Chain / Uncertainty Tree Diagram Available	Yes, traceability chain – No Uncertainty tree available

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	The uncertainty of the differential phase shift measurement is estimated to be around 0.5 mm, as noted in [RD-28], from the standard deviation of measurements at high altitudes, where no hydrometeor signal is present. In the lower part of the Atmosphere (<5km) the uncertainty ranges between 2-4mm, as state in [RD-28]. The information was provided a later stage, after the analysis was concluded.
References	Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4]

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	Ancillary data used in product generation, specified to some extent, though incomplete. A climatological model has been used as a priori to aid in the tracking of a GNSS signal but not documented. We received additional information in internal communication.
Ancillary Data Documentation	The climate models, it is a mix of MSIS (below 10 km) [RD-16], and BAIAP (above 10 km) [RD-12]. These models are used to provide a background bending angle profile used in the inversion (internal communication). Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4]

Product Generation

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>Data geolocation is calculated through the relative position of transmitter and receiver satellites with respect to the surface. A brief description of the satellite orbit estimation is provided. The orbit is determined through long, continuous, dual-frequency observations of multiple GNSS satellites (at least 4 simultaneous) to achieve orbit estimates of less than 20 cm. Typical accuracy estimates for Spire POD solutions are 10-25 cm 3-D RMS for position and 0.1-0.2 mm/s 3-D RMS for velocity.</p> <p>The profiles are geolocated through the latitude and longitude of perigee point at occultation point.</p> <p>The grading system is not entirely applicable to this mission type. L1D products provide also the area producing the signal associated to each altitude of the differential phase shift profile. We judge this fit for purpose.</p>
References	<p>Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description [RD-3] Spire Attitude and Navigation Product Summary [RD-7] Spire PRO Level 1 Product Description [RD-4]</p>

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Calibration algorithm (L0 to L1 product) is generally described in the Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description section Description. GNSS signals traversing the Earth's atmosphere during RO events are collected by Spire's receiver in low-Earth orbit using an open-loop tracking technique. The raw, open loop phase measurements and a priori model estimates are recorded and downlinked to the ground as rocObs files, forming the beginning of the RO processing chain. In order to derive atmospheric profiles of bending angle and refractivity from these raw measurements, the excess phase delay induced by the Earth's atmosphere must be derived for each time stamp. The a priori model employed is not reported or referenced in the documentation. A better description of the a priori model would increase the grade.</p>
References	<p>Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4]</p>

Retrieval Algorithm	
Grade: Not assessable	
Justification	This section is meant for L2 products.
References	N.A.

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not assessable	
Justification	No mission-specific processing documented.
Reference	N.A.

SPIRE GNSS-RO Evaluation

Table 2.3 SPIRE GNSS-RO Maturity Matrix

SPIRE GNSS-RO Data Provider Documentation Review				SPIRE GNSS-RO Validation Summary	Key
Product Information	Metrology		Product Generation		
Product Details	Measurement Validation Method	Not Assessed			
Availability & Accessibility	Not Assessable				
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Basic				
User Documentation	Good				
Ancillary Data					Excellent

SPIRE GNSS-RO Validation Maturity Matrix

Table 2.4 SPIRE GNSS-RO detailed validation

SPIRE GNSS-RO Detailed Validation				Key
Measurement		Geometric		
SPIRE GNSS-RO vs IGRA Validation Method	SPIRE GNSS-RO vs IGRA Validation Results Compliance	SPIRE GNSS-RO vs IGRA Geometric Validation Method	SPIRE GNSS-RO vs IGRA Geometric Validation Results Compliance	Not Assessed
				Not Assessable
				Basic
				Good
				Excellent
				Ideal
				Not Public

SPIRE GNSS-RO Data Provider Documentation Review

Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<i>Ideal All required information available.</i>
Product Name	SPIRE GNSS-PRO
Sensor Name	STRATOS
Sensor Type	GNSS Receiver
Mission Type	Constellation – 3 satellites
Mission Orbit	LEO Sun-synchronous 500 km altitude
Product Version Number	v6.02
Product ID	atmPrf
Processing level of product	Level 2
Measured Quantity Name	Refractivity, Dry Temperature, Dry Pressure
Measured Quantity Units	[1], [K], [hPa]
Stated Measurement Quality	<p>The differential phase observable has a precision of about 0.5 mm. Additionally; Level 2 radio occultation retrievals of atmospheric profiles are within the following thresholds:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Badness score: Profile must have a badness score of less than 45. Badness score is used to compute the overall confidence level of the RO profile before data assimilation into a weather model, which is stored in each bfrPrf file. • SNR: The SNR of the L1 signal must be greater than 80 V/V. The SNR of the L2 signal must be greater than 15 V/V. • Existence of reference satellite: There must be observations of at least 1 reference GNSS satellite during the occultation event.
Spatial Resolution	<p>Vertical: The nominal observed straight line tangent altitude range of each occultation event spans from less than -150 km to approximately 170 km for L1 data. Each atmPrf or bfrPrf product typically contains atmospheric profile data spanning from at least 80 km altitude to less than 0.5 km above the Earth’s surface. The original height interval is about 100 m, but the height in BUFR files is decimated to 200 m interval and it is truncated at 70 km.</p> <p>Horizontal: Although some information on horizontal resolution is given at page 8 of L2 description document, the exact value is not clearly reported. The coordinates of each point of the profiles retrieved are reported in the products, resulting in a distance between the top and bottom of the profile</p>

	<p>of about 100 km. For the characterization of the horizontal resolution, we can refer to L1 documentation: for each point provided in the vector of points within a profile, the spatial resolution is on the order of ~100 m vertically and ~10 km horizontally, see [RD-4] and [RD-28].</p> <p>We also received additional information from the data provider, stating that the nominal horizontal resolution should be of the order of [3x100] km, with the largest dimension corresponding to the projection of the profiles on the ground.</p>
Spatial Coverage	Global
Temporal Resolution	<p>An exact revisit time cannot be computed because the measurements are opportunistic in nature. A Spire PRO satellite orbiting in LEO and collecting GNSS transmissions will typically have measurements across a 100-1000 km wide swath depending on the tangent point altitude. As most Spire satellites are in high-inclination orbits, the Earth is regularly covered.</p> <p>Reference: [RD-4]</p>
Temporal Coverage	2023 – still ongoing
Point of Contact	Spire: Global Data and Analytics
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<p>Products available through ESA TPM portal:</p> <p>https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/announcement-of-opportunity/announcement-of-opportunity-for-spire-data</p> <p>https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/catalog/spire-live-and-historical-data</p>
Conditions for access and use	Commercial data; part of dataset is freely available through ESA Earth online: Spire live and historical data - Earth Online (esa.int)
Limitations on public access	Data available through ESA TPM portal
Product Abstract	GNSS-RO measurements of bending angle, temperature and pressure collected by three SPIRE GNSS-PRO satellites.

Availability & Accessibility							
Grade: Good							
Justification	Data partially follow FAIR principles. The grade can be upgrade to Excellent if the data management plan is provided						
Compliant with FAIR principles	Partially compliant						
	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="background-color: #f2f2f2;">To be Findable:</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier</td> <td>Yes, the file name is generated univocally</td> </tr> <tr> <td>data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	To be Findable:		(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Yes, the file name is generated univocally	data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	Yes
	To be Findable:						
(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Yes, the file name is generated univocally						
data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	Yes						

	metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes	Yes
	(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	No
	To be Accessible:	
	(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	Yes, on ESA portal
	the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	Yes, on ESA portal
	the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	Yes, on ESA portal
	metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	No
	To be Interoperable:	
	(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	Yes
	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	Yes
	(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	Yes, the file L1B that generates the data
	To be Reusable:	
	meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	Yes.
	(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	Yes
	R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	Yes
	R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	Yes
Data Management Plan	No	
Availability Status	Part of data are available on request to ESA Earth online portal. This dataset is distributed through FAIR principles.	

Product Format, Flags & Metadata	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Data are distributed in a documented standard file format. Includes a good set of documented metadata and data flags. Some variables should be more detailed described in the metadata or in the user guide, i.e., WLC variable.
Product File Format	<i>netCDF4, BUFR</i>
Metadata Conventions	L1 data file format is similar to the one used by the COSMIC Data Analysis and Archive Center (CDAAC) for the COSMIC-1 radio occultation mission.
Analysis Ready Data?	No

User Documentation		
Grade: Good		
Justification	Some PUG and ATBD-type information available, recovered from multiple documentation and internal communications. Documentation is up to date. Documentation is also partially compliant with QA4ECV.	
<i>Document</i>	<i>References</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spire PRO Level 1 Product Description • Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description • Talpe et al. 2025 [RD-28] 	<i>Partially</i>
ATBD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spire PRO Level 1 Product Description • Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description • Talpe et al. 2025 [RD-28] 	<i>Partially</i>

Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>Pre-flight and post-launch measurement calibration & characterisation efforts cover all reasonable aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is “fit for purpose” in terms of the mission’s stated performance.</p> <p>From documentation:</p> <p>The differential phase shift is affected by the antenna response. As noted in Talpe et al. (2025) and confirmed in Padullés et al. (2025), the response of antennas onboard Spire satellites was characterized on the ground, matched with on-orbit measurements, and shown to have little to no impact on the final differential phase shift observable. Therefore, the measurement can be considered properly calibrated. Future satellites will also undergo on-orbit antenna response characterization. Please see Section 3.c.1 in Talpe et al. (2025) for further details on antenna response and calibration.</p>

References	Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4] Talpe et al. 2025 [RD-28] Padullés et al. (2025) [RD-29]
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Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>The geometric characterization is done using GPS constellation data. The latitude and longitude coordinates are provided for each point of the vertical profiles in the product, although the algorithm makes it difficult to assign univocally the coordinates. Additionally, the L2 description document suggest using the perigee point as the best geolocation method for the retrieved profiles. See paragraph 2.2.2 Geolocation of RO Measurements of Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description [RD-3].</p> <p>Horizontal resolution is provided for L1 data, and it can be applied for L2 as well.</p> <p>In our judgement the method for calculating the geometrical location should be accurate using the GPS that is the best geolocation method so far. Each product has a footprint of tens of km projected on the surface; the geolocation method should be considered fit for purpose for such kind of application.</p>
References	<p>Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description [RD-3] Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4]</p>

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Traceability chain documented identifying most important steps and sources of uncertainty.
References	Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4]
Traceability Chain / Uncertainty Tree Diagram Available	Yes, traceability chain – No Uncertainty tree available

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Basic for Bending Angle	Grade: Not assessable for Temperate and Pressure
Justification	<p>The only uncertainty provided is on the bending angle, in form of the standard deviation of the BA values, calculated during the retrieval. Statistical comparison of the normalized bending angle difference between Spire profiles and ECMWF model output is presented in the documentation. The study should be used to calculate the mean accuracy and precision as function of the altitude. Pressure and Temperature uncertainties not provided.</p>
References	<p>Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description [RD-3] Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4]</p>

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Basic	
Justification	<p>Ancillary data used in product generation, specified to some extent, though incomplete.</p> <p>A climatological model has been cited in the L2 retrieval documentation without further explanations in the documentation. We received additional information in internal communication.</p>
Ancillary Data Documentation	<p>The climate models, it is a mix of MSIS (below 10 km) [RD-16], and BAIAP (above 10 km) [RD-12]. These models are used to provide a background bending angle profile used in the inversion.</p>

Product Generation

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>Data geolocation is calculated through the relative position of transmitter and receiver satellites with respect to the surface. A brief description of the satellite orbit estimation is provided. The orbit is determined through long, continuous, dual-frequency observations of multiple GNSS satellites (at least 4 simultaneous) to achieve orbit estimates of less than 20 cm. Typical accuracy estimates for Spire POD solutions are 10-25 cm 3-D RMS for position and 0.1-0.2 mm/s 3-D RMS for velocity.</p> <p>The profiles are geolocated through the latitude and longitude of perigee point at occultation point.</p> <p>The intercomparison exercise carried out in this work reveals that pressure and temperature profiles can be used above about 10 km altitude.</p> <p>Considering the horizontal scale of the pressure and temperature variation at tropopause and above, we judge fit for purpose the geometric processing.</p>
References	<p>Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description [RD-3] Spire Attitude and Navigation Product Summary [RD-7] Spire PRO Level 1 Product Description [RD-4]</p>

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Calibration algorithm (L0 to L1 product) is generally described in the Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description section Description. GNSS signals traversing the Earth's atmosphere during RO events are collected by Spire's receiver in low-Earth orbit using an open-loop tracking technique. The raw, open loop phase measurements and a priori model estimates are recorded and downlinked to the ground as rocObs files, forming the beginning of the RO processing chain. In order to derive atmospheric profiles of bending angle and refractivity from these raw measurements, the excess phase delay induced by the Earth's atmosphere must be derived for each time stamp. The a priori model employed is not reported or referenced in the documentation. A better description of the a priori model would increase the grade.</p>
References	Spire Level 1 PRO Product Description [RD-4]
Retrieval Algorithm	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>GNSS signal data collected from Spire's satellite constellation during radio occultation events (RO) are routinely processed into Level 2 data products containing vertical profiles of atmospheric bending angle, neutral refractivity, dry temperature, and dry pressure.</p> <p>Two versions of the neutral bending angle (BA) are evaluated: raw BA without statistical optimization and BA with statistical optimization. The optimized BA are used for the refractivity retrieval and raw BA are provided as primary RO observation for assimilation into forecasting models. Raw BA are preferable for assimilation because no climatology models are used during their derivation.</p> <p>The process of inverting the atmospheric excess phase delay (L1 data) and orbit positions to profiles of BA, atmospheric refractivity and temperature is well documented in research literature (articles cited on References).</p> <p>The dry profile is defined as an imaginable Earth atmosphere in hydrostatic equilibrium without moisture that provides the observed refractivity profile. Typically, the dry temperature is very close to the thermodynamic temperature at high altitudes, where the water vapor is negligible, but significantly smaller than the physical temperature in the lower troposphere.</p> <p>It should be noted that although products of dry temperature and refractivity are produced by the radio occultation inversion process, the product that has the most value to weather forecasting models is bending angle. This is because the retrieval of refractivity and dry temperature profiles from bending angle assumes a spherical symmetry of the atmosphere. The assumption decreases the value of these variables for assimilation by weather models because the atmosphere is not one-dimensional and often has strong horizontal variability. Hence, bending angle is usually selected as the primary radio occultation data product for weather model assimilation.</p>

	The retrieval algorithm is judged fit-for-purpose.
References	Spire Level 2 RO Atmospheric Profile Product Description [RD-3] Spire RO thermal profiles for climate studies: initial comparisons of the measurements from spire, NOAA-20 ATMS, Radiosonde, and COSMIC-2. [RD-31]

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not assessable	
Justification	No mission-specific processing documented.
Reference	N.A.

3. DETAILED VALIDATION

This section reports the results of the analyses carried out on SPIRE GNSS-PRO data for the study of precipitation and SPIRE GNSS-RO data for the study of atmospheric temperature and pressure profiles.

GNSS-PRO data analysis

The GNSS-PRO is an augmented technique of the standard RO. The receiver antenna registers both the horizontal (H) and vertical (V) components of the incoming radio waves. The first GNSS-PRO observations have been performed by the Spanish Aerospace Agency (*Agencia Espacial Española* AEE), with the Radio Occultation and Heavy Precipitation (ROHP) experiment aboard the PAZ satellite [RD-22]. In addition to the standard thermodynamic products, the phase difference between the H and V components contains information about the hydrometeors encountered along the ray path. The phase difference is induced by large size asymmetric hydrometeors, proportional to the rain rate [RD-23].

The observable describing the EM differential phase delay, per unit length, is the **specific differential phase shift** K_{dp} .

$$K_{dp} = \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi} \int \mathcal{R}(f_{hh} - f_{vv})N(D)dD \quad (mm \ km^{-1})$$

Where λ is the wavelength ($\sim 0.19 \text{ cm}$ for transmitter L1 frequency band, 1.575 GHz), $N(D)$ is the particle size distribution, f_{hh} and f_{vv} are the co-polar components of scattering amplitude matrix f , and \mathcal{R} indicates the real part.

The actual observable for Polarimetric Radio Occultation is defined as the **total differential phase shift**, given for each observation time $\Delta\Phi(t)$:

$$\Delta\Phi(t) = \Phi_h(t) - \Phi_v(t) = \int_L K_{dp}(l)dl \quad (mm) \text{ or } (rad)$$

Where $\Phi_h(t)$ and $\Phi_v(t)$ are the EM wave phase measured for the horizontal and vertical components, and L is the path length between transmitter (GNSS GEO satellite) and receiver (SPIRE LEO satellite) antennas [RD-24].

We received the **L1C_polPhs** dataset ($\sim 330\text{K}$ files, 634GB , 6 months of data), with the same spatial-temporal coverage of the **L2_patmPrf** dataset whose analysis is reported in the next paragraph. **L1C_polPhs** products provide not calibrated and not geolocated excess phase $\Phi_h(t)$ and $\Phi_v(t)$, given as a function of time. Variables as phase difference H-V $\Delta\Phi(t)$, and the occultation altitude are present but empty. Given these assumptions and SPIRE clarifications, the **L1C_polPhs** product is an intermediate processing level for internal use and doesn't contain the variables for studying the precipitation. However, we were still able to plot and visualize its content as we managed to retrieve the geolocation and occultation height arrays from the corresponding **L2_patmPrf** products. We evaluated the total differential phase shift $\Delta\Phi(t) = (h_{exl1,2} - v_{exl1,2})$, where $h_{exl1,2} = \Phi_h(t)$ and $v_{exl1,2} = \Phi_v(t)$, are **L1C_polPhs** variables corresponding to Excess Phase on L1 and L2 Channels for horizontal and vertical polarization respectively.

We then received 5 samples of levels **L1D_resPrf** and **L1D_hdrPhs** that contain calibrated and geolocated excess phase delay data, sampled at 1Hz and 50Hz respectively, meant for precipitation studies.

The **L1D_resPrf** dataset is built following the PAZ polarimetric radio occultation product for scientific applications, *resPrf* files [RD-25]. SPIRE **L1D_resPrf** variables are grouped as *Profiles* and *Rays*. Profiles comprise phase difference and RO data (T, P) as a function of height (1D).

Group Rays provides 2D information about phase difference. It has latitude and longitude grid and height, for graphical visualization of satellite acquisition. Phase difference in L1D_resPrf product is smoothed and filtered at 1Hz, where most of the information about the heavy precipitation is filtered out. The L1D_resPrf variable used in this analysis is *dph_smooth (mm)* which is the *smoothed differential phase shift* into a 0.1 km vertical grid.

The **L1D_hdrPhs** is an intermediate product between L1C_polPhs and L1D_resPrf that contains the excess phase delay sampled at the original frequency of 50 Hz like PAZ original product, more suitable for such applications. The content of L1D_hdrPhs doesn't present the same structure and variables of L1D_resPrf. The variable analysed is *Delta_phi_no_offset (rad)* which is the *differential excess delay after offset correction* given as a function of height.

L1D_resPrf and **L1D_hdrPhs** variables and product descriptions are described in *Summary Spire Level 1D Polarimetric RO Product Description [RD-8]*. An example of variables stored in both products are reported in Appendix (5). Figure 3.1 shows a table from [RD-8] that summarize the differences between SPIRE L1D products.

At L1C_polPhs processing stage, all variables are produced for both transmitter's frequency channels 1,2. But at subsequent stages (L1D_hdrPhs and L1D_resPrf), all variables are evaluated only for channel 1, related to frequency of 1.575 GHz ($\lambda \sim 0.19 \text{ cm}$).

	hdrPhs	resPrf
Indices	As a function of time	As a function of height: from 0 to 40 km
Index increment	50 Hz	0.1 km
Dimensions	Variable: Dependent on profile temporal length	Fixed: Always 400 points long
Inclusion of antenna coordinates	Yes	No
Inclusion of intermediary steps for corrected differential phase shift	Yes	No
Inclusion of thermodynamic Variables	No	Yes
Inclusion of raytracing	No	Yes

Figure 3.1 SPIRE L1D_hdrPhs and L1D_resPrf differences. Table from [RD-8].

The analysis of SPIRE-PRO data it is not a detailed validation, as the algorithm for deriving rain intensity from the excess phase delay has not yet been developed. Our analysis focuses on the content of the various products, the study of their variables, the review of relevant literature to identify which SPIRE product should be used in future precipitation studies. We compared the variables available in the different data processing levels and subsequently performed a comparison with GPM IMERG precipitation maps to distinguish rain events from clear-sky cases. Finally, we analysed the excess phase delay variables obtained from the **L1D_resPrf** and **L1D_hdrPhs** products to assess the differences in the signal between rain and clear-sky conditions.

GPM IMERG Final Precipitation L3 Half Hourly 0.1 x 0.1 deg V07, is composed of satellites observation from different platforms, employing both infrared and microwave measurements, with a spatial resolution of [0.1x0.1] deg (latitude/longitude) and a time resolution of 30 minutes [RD-20]. The GPM dataset presents a quality flag indicating also the instruments used for the measurement (*precipitationQualityIndex* in the product). All the examined data are marked with the value 0, indicating lower quality observations from infrared observations. Considering this, no screening has been applied on these reference data [RD-21].

Figure 3.2 to Figure 3.6 show the 2D SPIRE acquisitions (from now on Area of Interest AOI) with the corresponding IMERG precipitation map. SPIRE variable *dph_smooth* from the L1D_resPrf product allows visualization of the investigated region AOI, with the colour scale representing the altitude of the measurement (*red=low altitude, white=high altitude*). GNSS-PRO measurements are

acquired during an occultation event between the transmitting satellite and the SPIRE receiver. Therefore, the EM radiation probes higher altitudes at the beginning and end of the acquisition and lower altitudes in the central part of the acquisition. This geometry is typical of GNSS occultation techniques, resulting in a characteristic “smile” shape [RD-26]. Figure 3.7 shows a zoomed AOI that details how the acquisition is made. The AOI is made on N diagonal stripes that represents singular acquisitions. For each stripe, the delta excess phase is evaluated. Data are then processed, and one single delta excess phase profile is generated and associated with the entire 2D AOI (see the scheme in the bottom part of Figure 3.7).

SPIRE products were classified according to the amount of precipitation present in the AOI. SPIRE acquisition: 1) **Localized heavy rain**, the region of interest shows widespread precipitation, with precipitation intensity larger than 7 mm/hr in some areas; 2) and 3) **Localized rain**, a weak frontal system (<3 mm/hr) is present, but only a small portion of the SPIRE sounding region exhibits precipitation; 4) **Light rain**, widespread light precipitation (<2 mm/hr) is detected within the SPIRE sounding region; 5) **Clear sky**, the acquisition occurred in an area without precipitation.

From the comparison of all *delta excess phase* variables extracted from the **L1C_polPhs**, **L1D_resPrf**, and **L1D_hdrPhs** products (see Figure 3.8), it can be observed that the *delta excess phase* derived from the L1C_polPhs product displays a different scale compared with the variables at later processing stages, reflecting its raw nature. The *delta excess phase* is computed for both receiving channels, but at subsequent processing levels, only the variable from channel 1 is used. In Cases 1), 2), and 4), a clear separation is visible between the *delta excess phase* computed for channels 1 and 2, whereas in the other cases the variables overlap around zero.

Figure 3.9 shows only the calibrated *delta excess phase* variables from the L1D products. These plots allow a detailed appreciation of the differences between the two variables. The variable *Delta_phi_no_offset* (magenta curve) from the L1D_hdrPhs product is sampled at 50 Hz and contains more information than the *dph_smooth* variable (green curve), filtered at 1 Hz, from the L1D_resPrf, which is designed to be the final user-oriented data product. In many cases, a lack of continuity between the two variables can be observed. The green curve should follow the magenta curve trend since it's the smoothed curve; but in many spots the green curve has a different trend. The horizontal dashed-line indicate the altitude reported in the L1D_resPrf product as the variable *height_flag*, defined as follows: “*indicates the height below which the data are no longer considered reliable in terms of quality. It identifies jumps in the profile that were not corrected during the cycle slip correction process, often associated with tracking issues, low SNR, or uncorrected cycle slips that were not properly identified as such.*” [RD-23].

The presence of hydrometeor particles along the EM pulses path is expected to increase the phase difference, leading to a significant deviation from zero [RD-27]. Figure 3.9 shows that the *height_flag* is located at altitude of 6-8 km where the first significant excess phase variation occurs, in the tropospheric region, where the precipitation occurs. Therefore, according to the *height_flag* definition, all data below this altitude should be discarded from the analysis. In addition to this consideration, significant excess phase difference is present in every plots regardless of whether the precipitation intercepted in the AOI is heavy, light or absent.

The analysis carried out on the five **L1D_refPrf** and **L1D_hdrPhs** products do not consent to clearly appreciate the correlation between the signal distortion and the presence of hydrometers. However, we recommend a deeper analysis with a larger L1D dataset to understand the potentiality of the product.

Figure 3.2 SPIRE GNSS-PRO acquisition over localized heavy rain event, case 1).

Figure 3.3 SPIRE GNSS-PRO acquisition over localized rain event, case 2).

Figure 3.4 SPIRE GNSS-PRO acquisition over localized light rain event, case 3).

Figure 3.5 SPIRE GNSS-PRO acquisition over light rain event, case 4).

Figure 3.6 SPIRE GNSS-PRO acquisition with no rain event, case 5).

Figure 3.7 Top plot shows a zoom on SPIRE GNSS-PRO acquisition over localized heavy rain event, case 1). The 2D AOI is made of N stripes that sounds the atmosphere at different heights. Bottom scheme shows the processing steps for retrieving the delta excess phase profile for each acquisition. For each stripe the delta excess phase is retrieved and processed to obtain one single delta excess phase delay associated with the entire AOI.

Figure 3.8 Delta excess phase delay $\Delta\Phi(t)$ inside SPIRE products L1C_polPhs (not calibrated, evaluated for both transmitter's frequency channels), L1D_resPrf (calibrated and smoothed at 1Hz, channel 1) and L1D_hdrPhs (calibrated and sampled at 50Hz, the original acquisition frequency, channel 1).

Figure 3.9 Delta excess phase delay $\Delta\Phi(t)$ inside SPIRE L1D_resPrf (calibrated and smoothed at 1Hz green curve) and L1D_hdrPhs (calibrated and sampled at 50Hz, the original acquisition frequency, magenta curve).

GNSS-RO data validation

For the intercomparison exercise we received the SPIRE-RO observations from 15th May to 30th November 2023, global coverage, for a total of 253941 files received. The observations contain the temperature and pressure profiles obtained from radio-occultation (L2 data) and the bending angle profiles (L1 data), along with a series of metadata and information about satellite positioning, angles of view, impact parameter and flags. Each point of the profile has been identified with its altitude, latitude and longitude; the altitude grid changes for each observation.

The products contain also the **latitude and longitude of perigee point at occultation point** which is suggested by SPIRE to be used to geolocate the profile; we followed this indication and to simplify the intercomparison, the profiles have been treated as vertical observations above these coordinates.

The selected reference is the Integrated Global Radiosonde Archive (IGRA) network [RD-15]; radiosondes measurements can be considered an optimal test reference for pressure and temperature collected during the balloon flight. IGRA dataset consists of radiosonde and pilot balloon observations from more than 2800 stations around the globe with nearly 800 stations that provide real time data. Observations are available at standard and variable pressure levels, fixed and variable-height wind levels, and the surface and tropopause. Variables include pressure, temperature, geopotential height, relative humidity, dew point depression, wind direction and speed, and elapsed time since launch.

Figure 3.10 Average weight of observations in statical optimization parameter of the data used in the comparison. The shaded area represents the min and max values available.

The radiosonde profiles in this intercomparison have been treated as vertical profiles localized using station coordinates. Generally, a radiosonde reaches a maximum altitude of 40-50 km, with a variable altitude grid. The measurements are reported to fixed pressure levels, with a larger resolution with respect to SPIRE. For this reason, we decided for the comparison to linearly

interpolate the SPIRE results into the IGRA altitude grid, to avoid oversampling the reference profiles.

The upper part of the SPIRE profile (above 50 km) is generally highly influenced by the a-priori used in the retrieval process. SPIRE data reports the weight of observations in statistical optimization; this value indicates the percentage of influence of the observations with respect to the a-priori used in the retrieval.

Figure 3.10 shows the average weights of data employed in this work, together with its maximum and minimum values, identified by the shaded area. In this work we decided to employ data with a weight of observation above 0.8, threshold reached generally between 40 and 50 km. This threshold has been selected basing on scientific literature [RD-17, RD-18].

Thresholds selection and geographical division

Several combinations of spatial and temporal thresholds have been tested, to optimize the number of couples for the intercomparison. The table 3.1 reports the number of couples found for the several threshold combinations tested.

We decided to employ a spatial threshold of 100 km and a temporal threshold of 1 hours, due to the large number of co-locations found. These values could introduce a large uncertainty for the tropospheric observations, but as will be shown in this study, SPIRE data below 7-10 km present a large bias, making them unfeasible for scientific usage. The one-hour temporal threshold should reduce the impact of night-day difference; the spatial threshold has been selected considering the large horizontal scale of the upper parts of the atmosphere, characterized by a large horizontal homogeneity with respect to the troposphere; the largest number of measurements are in the east Asia and Europe. Figure 3.11 shows the map of co-located measurements obtained with the spatial and temporal thresholds applied. The selected thresholds yield to 1260 co-located SPIRE-IGRA couples.

Measurements employed in the study have been filtered according to the SPIRE metadata quality flag (i.e., Badness Score <35, equal to good quality). This results in a total of 861 SPIRE-IGRA couples emplaced in the analysis, resulting in filtering out 31% of data due to low quality. Table 3.2 reports the distribution of measurements collected by each SPIRE receiver, almost 50% of data comes from satellite FM 166. For study the latitudinal dependency of the results, the globe has been divided into seven areas according to the latitude and reported in Table 3.3. Figure 3.12 reports the number of couples as function of the altitude for the several geographical areas. The upper part of the profiles characterized by a lower number of couples due to the presence of less radiosondes reaching these altitudes.

Table 3.1 List of all temporal and spatial thresholds tested in order to obtain co-located measurements for the intercomparison.

Temporal and spatial thresholds	Number of couples
15 km, 1 hour	31
25 km, 1 hour	79
50 km, 1 hour	299
100 km, 1 hour	1260
100 km, 3 hours	4771

Figure 3.11 Map of the co-located measurements of SPIRE and IGRA for the intercomparison (orange dots). The spatial and temporal thresholds applied are 100 km, 1hour. The total couples obtained are 1260.

Table 3.2 Number of SPIRE GNSS-PRO measurements collected by each satellite emplaced in the study.

SPIRE GNSS-PRO satellites	Number of occurrences	[%] occurrences
FM 166	419	49
FM 167	245	28
FM 170	197	23

Table 3.3 Latitudinal regions to study the latitudinal dependency of measurements. The statistical intercomparison has been performed globally and for each region.

Area name	Min-Max latitude [deg]
South polar	-90, -60
South temperate	-60, -35
South tropical	-35, -15

Equatorial	-15, 15
North tropical	15, 35
North temperate	35, 60
North polar	60, 90

Figure 3.12 Number of couples SPIRE-IGRA as a function of altitude. The analysis has been performed at different latitudinal regions. The north pole and temperate regions present the higher matching.

Temperature profiles

The average temperature profiles and standard deviation (shaded area) observed for the identified latitudinal areas (see Table 3.3) are report from Figure 3.13 to Figure 3.16. In the [0,10] km altitude region, SPIRE measurements are affected by a large negative bias. This bias is present in all latitudinal regions except for the south pole, where this bias appears less evident. At lower altitudes (typically below 5-7km), SPIRE data lead to unphysical results: temperature inversion in the profiles and very low surface temperature (i.e., $\sim -40^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 0 km). Such results are due to the absence of water vapor in the a priori model used in the retrieval algorithm.

The observation in the troposphere is highly dependent on the climatological model used in the retrieval. Considering the systematic negative nature of the bias, this is also not be accountable for the distance between radiosonde and SPIRE data, that should introduce a random uncertainty. The water vapor as cause of this large bias is also suggested by the better agreement of the south

polar region (Figure 3.14); in fact, the south pole is extremely dry and characterized by a very low amount of water vapor. Furthermore, the bias is more pronounced for the tropics and equatorial regions, characterized by a greater amount of humidity.

The upper region of the profiles, up to 30 km, are characterized by a good agreement with IGRA data, likely due to the negligible amount of water vapor at higher altitudes. In the [10,30] km altitude region, the average bias is within 2 K, with a standard deviation within 2 K. Above 30 km, temperature profiles are characterized by higher oscillations, probably due to the low number of couples at these altitudes.

Due to the lack of uncertainties in the products (absent in both SPIRE and IGRA), the average bias and difference standard deviation should be used as an estimate of systematic and random uncertainties. In this context, the IGRA uncertainty are negligible with respect to the SPIRE data. The evaluated differences SPIRE-IGRA have been reported in Figure 3.17 and more in detail for each latitudinal in Figure 3.18 and Figure 3.19, where the shaded area represents the standard deviation of the difference.

Figure 3.13 temperature average profiles of co-located SPIRE and IGRA measurements. (left graph), temperature average profiles of the equatorial region (right graph).

Figure 3.14 temperature average profiles of co-located SPIRE and IGRA measurements for the north and south polar regions.

Figure 3.15 temperature average profiles of co-located SPIRE and IGRA measurements for the tropical regions.

Figure 3.16 temperature average profiles of co-located SPIRE and IGRA measurements for the temperate regions.

Figure 3.17 Mean temperature difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles. The shaded areas are the standard deviation associated to mean temperature difference.

Figure 3.18 Mean temperature difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles for all and equatorial regions (left panel) and north and south tropical regions (right panel). Here is highlighted the 5-45km altitude profiles, that is physically interesting for the intercomparison. The shaded areas are the standard deviation associated to mean temperature difference.

Figure 3.19 Mean temperature difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles for temperate regions (left panel) and polar regions (right panel). Here is highlighted the 5-45km altitude profiles, that is physically interesting for the intercomparison. The shaded areas are the standard deviation associated to mean temperature difference.

Figure 3.20 reports the histogram of differences evaluated at varying altitude. The [%] of occurrence has been calculated using the total number of available couples at specific altitude. The curves from 10 to 25 km have a gaussian shape with a central value within [-0.5, 0.5] K, with half width at half maximum of about 1 K. The 30 km curve reports a larger bias (1 K) and dispersion, while the upper profiles are characterized by oscillations due to the low number of couples. Data in troposphere presents large negative differences (5 and 10 km curves).

Figure 3.20 SPIRE-IGRA temperature difference histograms evaluated at varying altitudes between 5 and 40 km. right panel shows in detail the area with majority of occurrences.

Pressure profiles

In this section are reported all the analysis conducted on pressure profiles. The results are similar to those obtained for temperature. Figure 3.21 shows the average pressure profiles of SPIRE and IGRA. This type of data visualization is not effective for pressure, leading to a possible misinterpretation of data. For this reason, Figure 3.21 has been reported for completeness but the mean difference SPIRE-IGRA is more effective to visualize and highlight the differences. Figure 3.22 shows the mean difference and standard deviation evaluated for all altitude profiles and latitudinal regions. A detailed view of [0,40] km for each profile can be found in Figure 3.23 and Figure 3.24. In the [10,30] km altitude region, SPIRE and IGRA data are in good agreement, showing a low bias with a maximum difference of -1 hPa at 10km in the north polar region (see

right panel of Figure 3.24). The biggest biases are found in the region below 10 km (up to 150 hPa), leading to unphysical results, not suitable for usage (i.e., 1200 hPa at 0 km). The south polar region is an exception, it is characterized by a reduced bias in the troposphere, suggesting the water vapor not accounted in the retrieval algorithm as the cause of the discrepancy. To highlight the pressure bias between SPIRE and IGRA, it is also evaluated as a relative quantity, expressed in [%], reported in Figure 3.25 to Figure 3.27.

Figure 3.21 Pressure average equatorial profiles of co-located SPIRE and IGRA measurements.

Figure 3.22 Mean pressure difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles. The shaded areas are the standard deviation associated to mean pressure difference.

Figure 3.23 Mean pressure difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles for all and equatorial regions (left panel) and north and south tropical regions (right panel). Here is highlighted the 5-45km altitude regions, that is physically interesting for the intercomparison. The shaded areas are the standard deviation associated to mean pressure difference.

Figure 3.24 Mean pressure difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles for temperate regions (left panel) and polar regions (right panel). Here is highlighted the 5-45km altitude regions, that is physically interesting for the intercomparison. The shaded areas are the standard deviation associated to mean pressure difference.

Figure 3.25 Mean relative pressure difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles. The shaded areas are the standard deviation associated to mean pressure difference.

Figure 3.26 Mean relative pressure difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles for all and equatorial regions (left panel) and tropical regions (right panel). Here is highlighted the 5-45km altitude regions, that is physically interesting for the intercomparison. The shaded areas are the associated standard deviation.

Figure 3.27 Mean relative pressure difference evaluated for SPIRE and IGRA average profiles for temperate regions (left panel) and polar regions (right panel). Here is highlighted the 5-

45km altitude regions, that is physically interesting for the intercomparison. The shaded areas are the associated standard deviation.

The pressure difference histograms at several altitudes are reported in Figure 3.28. The curves of the upper altitudes (above 25 km altitude) present a central value within 0.1 hPa from the ideal case with half width at half maximum of about 0.2 hPa. The 10, 15 and 20 km altitude curves show larger dispersion approaching the tropopause. The 5 km curve is characterized by large positive differences with respect to IGRA.

Figure 3.28 SPIRE-IGRA pressure difference histograms evaluated at varying altitudes between 5 and 45 km. right panel shows in detail the area with majority of occurrences.

Fit results

In this section are summarized the statistical analysis performed on both temperature and pressure parameters. The linear regression and correlation coefficient between SPIRE and IGRA profiles have been computed as a function of altitudes. Figure 3.29 and Figure 3.30 report how fit slopes and intercepts varies with altitude; Figure 3.31 shows the correlation coefficient. The [10,30] km altitude region is characterized by high values of correlation coefficient (i.e., >0.95), with a fit slope and intercept closer to the ideal values (1 and 0 respectively). The fit results worsen in the troposphere (below 12 km altitude), with a correlation coefficient rapidly decreasing approaching the surface. At altitudes above 30 km, the curves are characterized by oscillations that are probably caused by the reduced number of couples.

Figure 3.29 Slope results of linear regression evaluated between SPIRE and IGRA as a function of altitude.

Figure 3.30 Intercepts of the linear regression evaluated between SPIRE and IGRA as a function of altitude.

Figure 3.31 Correlation coefficient evaluated between SPIRE and IGRA profiles as a function of altitude.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This work presents the validation of SPIRE GNSS-PRO and GNSS-RO data (dry Temperature and Pressure).

Products are generally well documented. Several entries of the maturity matrix can reach better grades, by integrating some information in the documentation and improving the description in the metadata.

SPIRE GNSS PRO

The analysis of **SPIRE-PRO data is a preliminary investigation** of their suitability for precipitation studies and the identification of heavy precipitation events, **as the algorithm to derive rain intensity from excess phase delay is not already formalized by the wider scientific community**. However, it is recognized that differential phase shift is correlated with the presence of hydrometers, such as rain droplets, ice crystals, etc. [Padullés et al., 2024].

We made a **comparison** of SPIRE variables **from different processing levels** (*L1C_polPhs*, *L1D_resPrf* and *L1D_hdrPhs*), and with GPM IMERG precipitation maps we classified the acquisitions according to precipitation intensity. *L1C_polPhs* is **not meant for the users**, as it is an internal processing stage that doesn't include geolocation, nor the calibrated data. We then focused our analysis over L1D products. Variable *Delta_phi_no_offset* from *L1D_hdrPhs* product is sampled at 50 Hz while *dph_smooth* variable present in *L1D_resPrf* is filtered at 1 Hz is meant for distribution to users. In our opinion, **the variable at 50Hz contains more information** and is more suitable for such studies, since the smoothing process could eliminate valuable information, as demonstrated with [roho-PAZ mission](#). **The delta excess phase curves, linked with possible precipitation, show that significant signal variations occur in the bottom part of the profile (between 0 and 6-8km of altitude), which is the region of the atmosphere where precipitation events occur**. However, for all 5 samples examined, these variations are found below the *height_flag* value, and according to its definition, **all data below such height should be discarded due to reduced reliability**.

Significant variation in the delta excess phase difference were observed in all five cases, regardless of precipitation intensity or presence of rain, with larger variations characterizing the "localized heavy rain" event. **A clear correlation between the presence of the hydrometeors and the delta excess phase is well documented in literature** [RD-23], [RD-24],[RD-25],[RD-29]; **but it cannot be established through the analysis of the five samples provided**. We suggest to better characterize the usage of variable *height_flag*, and to conduct a deeper analysis on a larger L1D dataset.

We also did a comparison between the information content of SPIRE *L1D_resPrf* file format and the corresponding *PAZ_resPrf* product (where all the values are smoothed at 1 Hz and the products are in NetCDF), The following conclusions are derived:

- The content is almost the same, even if *Global_Attributes* differ, being the *PAZ_resPrf* less complete
- The *Group: Profile* from PAZ data contains all atmospheric parameters (temperature, pressure, refractivity, specific humidity, relative humidity, geopotential height above MSL and water vapour pressure) derived from UCAR wetPf2 COSMIC (Constellation Observing System for Meteorology Ionosphere and Climate) mission. Atmospheric data are those provided in SPIRE *L2_patmPrf* data interpolated into 0.1 km vertical grid.

What we can consider missing on SPIRE side is:

- an exact corresponding product to *PAZ_polPhs* product, which contain the 'Corrected differential phase at 50 Hz'. On the contrary, SPIRE *L1C_polPhs* product does not contain this value at this resolution. In SPIRE *L1D_hdrPhs* it is present, but only smoothed at 1 Hz.

- other parameters such as 'Calibrated differential phase shift' (using linear trend or antenna pattern) are not given at all in SPIRE product.

We suggest aligning SPIRE product as much as possible to PAZ definitions, as the current users of these experimental products are already used to that format, and also because some very useful information at 50 Hz are not provided.

SPIRE GNSS-RO

SPIRE GNSS-RO data are compared with data from the IGRA radiosonde network. The data are coupled using temporal and spatial thresholds of 100 km and 1 hour, resulting in 1260 SPIRE-IGRA coupled measurements; data have been also screened using quality flags, for a total of 861 couples employed in the study. The intercomparison and statistical analysis are conducted by grouping results based on latitudinal zones and by altitude within the profiles. This regional division allowed for more precise results, accounting for atmospheric variability across different regions and at varying altitudes.

The "*weight of observations in statistical optimization*" (WO) shown in Figure 3.10, is a parameter provided by SPIRE that describes the influence of measurements on the a priori model used for retrieval. We decided to further screen the profiles, selecting values with WO above 0.8 (a-priori influence on results less than 20%). This screening ensures the validation of actual measurements from SPIRE, avoiding comparisons of the a-priori model with IGRA. The 0.8 threshold usually excludes measurements above 45 km altitude, where the a priori model has an increasingly significant influence with altitude.

The temperature results suggest that SPIRE and IGRA data are in good agreement, particularly in the [10,30] km altitude region. Below 10 km, SPIRE measurements tend to diverge from the reference, yielding values that lack physical interpretation. SPIRE data are not representative at lower altitudes due to the absence of water vapor in the a priori model used in the retrieval algorithm. This explanation is supported by the fact that SPIRE measurements in the South Polar region exhibit low divergence, as water vapor concentration in this region is much depleted (generally, the South Pole presents a very low amount of humidity during winter, [RD-19]). This divergence is expected and well-documented. The linear regression results further support these findings; between 10 and 30 km altitude, the slope and intercept approach 1 and 0, respectively. Additionally, the correlation coefficient for these altitudes exceeds 0.95.

The analyses of pressure profiles show good agreement between SPIRE and IGRA data above 10 km altitude. Similar to temperature profiles, pressure measurements in the troposphere yield values that lack physical meaning. As shown in Figure 3.25, the relative pressure difference exceeds 5%, reaching up to 15%. Statistical results confirm this trend, with the best agreement between SPIRE and IGRA observed in the [10,30] km altitude region, regardless of the latitudinal region.

The intercomparison between SPIRE and IGRA shows excellent agreement in the 10-30 km altitude region, diverging widely below 10 km. Profiles above 30 km present some oscillations, probably due to the low number of radiosondes reaching these upper altitudes.

The grade assigned for the validation activity compliance is good; we suggest justifying the bias in the troposphere in the documentation, maybe adding a flag indicating the quality of the profiles or their usability at the various altitudes. We also suggest adding more precise and clear description of the variables in the documentation, that are not immediately understandable by a generic user (e.g., the weight of observations in statistical optimization).

5. APPENDIX

L1D_resPrf product variables:

```
Netcdf resPrf_2025-04-22T08-23-44Z.363894787.236.G14 {
```

```
// global attributes:
```

```
:processing_center = "Spire Processing Center";
```

```
:proc_version = "v06.04";
```

```
:mission = "Spire";
```

```
:creation_time = "2025-04-22 09:44:52 UTC";
```

```
:title = "GNSS-PRO calibrated differential excess phase";
```

```
:setting = "rising";
```

```
:lat_occ = 15.4965068742095;
```

```
:lon_occ = -154.679365722051;
```

```
:az_surf = -158.481632964719;
```

```
:leo_sat = 236;
```

```
:timeUTC = "08:23:46";
```

```
:history = "derived from:\nspire_gnss-pro_L1D_hdrPhs_v06.04_2025-04-22T08-23-44_FM236_G14.nc on 2025-04
```

```
22T08-23-44";
```

```
group: profiles {
```

```
dimensions:
```

```
height_res = 400;
```

```
variables:
```

```
float height(height_res);
```

```
height:long_name = "Height above the mean sea level (MSL)";
```

```
height:units = "km";
```

```
float dph_smooth(height_res);
```

```
dph_smooth:long_name = "Smoothed differential phase shift into 0.1 km vertical grid";
```



```
dph_smooth:units = "mm" ;

float dph_smooth_std(height_res) ;

dph_smooth_std:long_name = "Standard deviation of the smoothed differential phase shift into
0.1 km vertical grid" ;

dph_smooth_std:units = "mm" ;

float temperature(height_res) ;

temperature:long_name = "Dry temperature from L2 patmPrf interpolated into 0.1 km vertical
grid" ;

temperature:units = "K" ;

float pressure(height_res) ;

pressure:long_name = "Dry pressure from L2 patmPrf interpolated into 0.1 km vertical grid" ;

pressure:units = "mbar" ;

float refractivity(height_res) ;

refractivity:long_name = "Refractivity from L2 patmPrf interpolated into 0.1 km vertical grid" ;

refractivity:units = "N" ;

// group attributes:

:height_flag = 5.52568201687041 ;

:deltaphi_10km = -15.5693878295392 ;

:deltaphi_15km = -9.6744901597321 ;

:deltaphi_max = 0.687260863836333 ;

:deltaphi_max_height = 1.4 ;

:deltaphi_rms20 = 1.94382918462896 ;

:deltaphi_top_height = 999LL ;

:deltaphi_top_height_thresh = 0.64955398591038 ;

} // group profiles

group: rays {

dimensions:

nray = 220 ;
```

```
npoint = 301 ;  
  
variables:  
  
float Latitude(nray, npoint) ;  
  
Latitude:units = "deg" ;  
  
Latitude:long_name = "latitude" ;  
  
float Longitude(nray, npoint) ;  
  
Longitude:units = "deg" ;  
  
Longitude:long_name = "longitude" ;  
  
float Height(nray, npoint) ;  
  
Height:units = "km" ;  
  
Height:long_name = "height" ;  
  
} // group rays  
  
}
```

L1D_polPhs product variables:

```
netcdf hdrPhs_2025-04-22T00-34-47Z.409907662.236.R05 {  
  
dimensions:  
  
height_MSL = 2327 ;  
  
variables:  
  
double height_MSL(height_MSL) ;  
  
height_MSL:units = "km" ;  
  
panopanolpy  
  
height_MSL:long_name = "Ray-averaged tangent point altitude with respect to mean sea  
level" ;  
  
double latitude(height_MSL) ;  
  
latitude:units = "degrees_North" ;  
  
latitude:long_name = "Tangent point latitude" ;  
  
double longitude(height_MSL) ;  
  
longitude:units = "degrees_East" ;
```

```
longitude:long_name = "Tangent point longitude" ;

double occ_azimuth(height_MSL) ;

occ_azimuth:units = "deg" ;

occ_azimuth:long_name = "Azimuth on the tangent plane of the direction towards GNSS
w.r.t North, clockwise" ;

float Num_rays(height_MSL) ;

Num_rays:units = "1" ;

Num_rays:long_name = "Number of occultation rays averaged" ;

double antenna_inclination_angle(height_MSL) ;

antenna_inclination_angle:units = "deg" ;

antenna_inclination_angle:long_name = "Angle of arrival with respect to the nadir-looking
direction of the antenna

axial dimension (+Z)" ;

double antenna_azimuth_angle(height_MSL) ;

antenna_azimuth_angle:units = "deg" ;

antenna_azimuth_angle:long_name = "Angle of arrival with respect to the normal
direction to the plane of the

antenna (+X), contained in the plane Z=0 (i.e. plane orthogonal to the axial direction of the
antenna)" ;

// global attributes:

:processing_center = "Spire Processing Center" ;

:proc_version = "v06.03" ;

:mission = "Spire" ;

:creation_time = "2025-04-22 01:45:49 UTC" ;

:title = "GNSS-PRO data based on calibrated differential excess phase" ;

:version = "v06.03" ;

:setting = "rising" ;

:bScore = 22.5757872761721 ;

:bad = 0 ;

:rgeoid = 0.0107395074446033 ;
```

```
:curv_offset = 17.8346903017891, -9.17190929064509, 10.595525510993 ;  
:rfict = 6360.7604153156 ;  
:Tocc = 60.2139105075751 ;  
:lat = -36.5371294256144 ;  
:lon = -27.3260086493784 ;  
:azimuth = 162.142084700767 ;  
:leo_sat = 236 ;  
:filestamp = "236.2025.112.00.34.R05" ;  
:occ_sat = "R05" ;  
:con_id = "R" ;  
:frequency_Hz_L1 = 1602562500 ;  
:frequency_Hz_L2 = 1246437500 ;  
:meanSNR_L1 = 5319.66 ;  
:meanSNR_L2 = 4393.76 ;  
:noise_L1_applied = 96.4 ;  
:noise_L2_applied = 78.4 ;  
:h_meanSNR_L1 = 3586.65 ;  
:v_meanSNR_L1 = 3937.07 ;  
:h_meanSNR_L2 = 2713.05 ;  
:v_meanSNR_L2 = 3501.83 ;  
:day_of_year = 112 ;  
:day = 22 ;  
:date = "2025-04-22" ;  
:month = 4 ;  
:year = 2025 ;  
:start_time_UTC = "00:34:49" ;  
:start_time_GPS = "1429317307.0128756" ;  
:mean_PhiDP_nocorr_rad_3_10_km = 0.484888087514477 ;  
:occ_az = 162.039161465869 ;
```

:mean_ant_az = -8.00672422677459 ;

:pass_qc = 1LL ;

:az_qc = 1LL ;

:mps_qc = 1LL ;

:ro_qc = 1LL ;

:pdjumps_qc = 1LL ;

:history = "derived from:\nspire_gnss-pro_L1C_polPhs_v06.03_2025-04-22T00-34-47_FM236_R05.nc on 2025-04

22T00-34-47\nspire_gnss-pro_L2_patmPrf_v06.03_2025-04-22T00-34-47_FM236_R05.nc on 2025-04-22T00-34

47\nspire_att_L1A_leoAtt_v06.01_2025-04-21T22-57-00_FM236.log on 2025-04-21T22-57-00" ;

group: RO_arc {

dimensions:

time_low_res = 124 ;

variables:

float time_low_res(time_low_res) ;

time_low_res:units = "s" ;

time_low_res:long_name = "Time low resolution 1 sec for the entire RO arc" ;

float v_SNR_1s_arc(time_low_res) ;

v_SNR_1s_arc:units = "0.1 Volt/Volt" ;

v_SNR_1s_arc:long_name = "SNR profile for vertical polarization, low res, full arc" ;

float h_SNR_1s_arc(time_low_res) ;

h_SNR_1s_arc:units = "0.1 Volt/Volt" ;

h_SNR_1s_arc:long_name = "SNR profile for horizontal polarization, low res, full arc" ;

float SNR_ratio_1s_arc(time_low_res) ;

SNR_ratio_1s_arc:units = "1" ;

SNR_ratio_1s_arc:long_name = "SNR V/H ratio profile, low res, full arc" ;

} // group RO_arc

```
group: Processing_default {  
  
  variables:  
  
    float Delta_phi_raw(height_MSL) ;  
  
    Delta_phi_raw:long_name = "Differential excess delay H minus V" ;  
  
    Delta_phi_raw:units = "rad" ;  
  
    float Delta_phi_cs(height_MSL) ;  
  
    Delta_phi_cs:long_name = "Differential excess delay after cycle slip correction" ;  
  
    Delta_phi_cs:units = "rad" ;  
  
    float PhiDP_cs(height_MSL) ;  
  
    PhiDP_cs:long_name = "Phase shift after cycle slip correction, 1 second average" ;  
  
    PhiDP_cs:units = "rad" ;  
  
    float Delta_phi_no_offset(height_MSL) ;  
  
    Delta_phi_no_offset:long_name = "Differential excess delay after offset correction" ;  
  
    Delta_phi_no_offset:units = "rad" ;  
  
    float PhiDP_no_offset(height_MSL) ;  
  
    PhiDP_no_offset:long_name = "Phase shift after cycle slip correction, 1 second  
average" ;  
  
    PhiDP_no_offset:units = "rad" ;  
  
    float time(height_MSL) ;  
  
    time:long_name = "Time" ;  
  
    time:units = "s" ;  
  
} // group Processing_default  
  
}  
  
// global attributes:  
  
:processing_center = "Spire Processing Center" ;  
  
:proc_version = "v06.03" ;  
  
:mission = "Spire" ;  
  
:creation_time = "2025-04-22 01:45:49 UTC" ;
```

```
:title = "GNSS-PRO data based on calibrated differential excess phase" ;  
:version = "v06.03" ;  
:setting = "rising" ;  
:bScore = 22.5757872761721 ;  
:bad = 0 ;  
:rgeoid = 0.0107395074446033 ;  
:curv_offset = 17.8346903017891, -9.17190929064509, 10.595525510993 ;  
:rfict = 6360.7604153156 ;  
:Tocc = 60.2139105075751 ;  
:lat = -36.5371294256144 ;  
:lon = -27.3260086493784 ;  
:azimuth = 162.142084700767 ;  
:leo_sat = 236 ;  
:filestamp = "236.2025.112.00.34.R05" ;  
:occ_sat = "R05" ;  
:con_id = "R" ;  
:frequency_Hz_L1 = 1602562500 ;  
:frequency_Hz_L2 = 1246437500 ;  
:meanSNR_L1 = 5319.66 ;  
:meanSNR_L2 = 4393.76 ;  
:noise_L1_applied = 96.4 ;  
:noise_L2_applied = 78.4 ;  
:h_meanSNR_L1 = 3586.65 ;  
:v_meanSNR_L1 = 3937.07 ;  
:h_meanSNR_L2 = 2713.05 ;  
:v_meanSNR_L2 = 3501.83 ;  
:day_of_year = 112 ;  
:day = 22 ;  
:date = "2025-04-22" ;
```

```
:month = 4 ;  
  
:year = 2025 ;  
  
:start_time_UTC = "00:34:49" ;  
  
:start_time_GPS = "1429317307.0128756" ;  
  
:mean_PhiDP_nocorr_rad_3_10_km = 0.484888087514477 ;  
  
:occ_az = 162.039161465869 ;  
  
:mean_ant_az = -8.00672422677459 ;  
  
:pass_qc = 1LL ;  
  
:az_qc = 1LL ;  
  
:mps_qc = 1LL ;  
  
:ro_qc = 1LL ;  
  
:pdjumps_qc = 1LL ;  
  
:history = "derived from:\nspire_gnss-pro_L1C_polPhs_v06.03_2025-04-22T00-34-  
47_FM236_R05.nc on 2025-04-  
  
22T00-34-47\nspire_gnss-pro_L2_patmPrf_v06.03_2025-04-22T00-34-  
47_FM236_R05.nc on 2025-04-22T00-34-  
  
47\nspire_att_L1A_LeoAtt_v06.01_2025-04-21T22-57-00_FM236.log on 2025-04-21T22-  
57-00" ;  
  
group: RO_arc {  
  
  dimensions:  
  
    time_low_res = 124 ;  
  
  variables:  
  
    float time_low_res(time_low_res) ;  
  
    time_low_res:units = "s" ;  
  
    time_low_res:long_name = "Time low resolution 1 sec for the entire RO arc" ;  
  
    float v_SNR_1s_arc(time_low_res) ;  
  
    v_SNR_1s_arc:units = "0.1 Volt/Volt" ;  
  
    v_SNR_1s_arc:long_name = "SNR profile for vertical polarization, low res, full arc" ;  
  
    float h_SNR_1s_arc(time_low_res) ;  
  
    h_SNR_1s_arc:units = "0.1 Volt/Volt" ;
```

```
h_SNR_1s_arc:long_name = "SNR profile for horizontal polarization, low res, full arc" ;  
float SNR_ratio_1s_arc(time_low_res) ;  
SNR_ratio_1s_arc:units = "1" ;  
SNR_ratio_1s_arc:long_name = "SNR V/H ratio profile, low res, full arc" ;  
} // group RO_arc  
group: Processing_default {  
variables:  
float Delta_phi_raw(height_MSL) ;  
Delta_phi_raw:long_name = "Differential excess delay H minus V" ;  
Delta_phi_raw:units = "rad" ;  
float Delta_phi_cs(height_MSL) ;  
Delta_phi_cs:long_name = "Differential excess delay after cycle slip correction" ;  
Delta_phi_cs:units = "rad" ;  
float PhiDP_cs(height_MSL) ;  
PhiDP_cs:long_name = "Phase shift after cycle slip correction, 1 second average" ;  
PhiDP_cs:units = "rad" ;  
float Delta_phi_no_offset(height_MSL) ;  
Delta_phi_no_offset:long_name = "Differential excess delay after offset correction" ;  
Delta_phi_no_offset:units = "rad" ;  
float PhiDP_no_offset(height_MSL) ;  
PhiDP_no_offset:long_name = "Phase shift after cycle slip correction, 1 second  
average" ;  
PhiDP_no_offset:units = "rad" ;  
float time(height_MSL) ;  
time:long_name = "Time" ;  
time:units = "s" ;  
} // group Processing_default  
}
```


[END OF DOCUMENT]